

A STUDY OF OUT OF HOME (OOH) MEDIA AND SUSTAINABLE MARKETING

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Abstract

Marketing strategies and business are two side of a same coin, evolution of marketing has begun right from the ancient phenomenon of mercantilism to millennials of 21st century. Marketing research and its philosophies are very important if it needs to survive in any scenario whether its traditional or modern out of Home (OOH) Media modes of advertisements, both have to relate how it could maintain code of ethics related to sustainability marketing with a correlation of business strategies and saving the environment.

This paper is an attempt to find out how marketing management, Out of Home (OOH) Media studies can make contribution towards development of sustainability marketing to help the living organisms and nature having rights to heal themselves.

Key Words: *Out of Home (OOH) Media, Sustainable, Marketing.*

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Introduction:

Sustainability of Marketing is not a new phenomenon in recent days. Since the years 1980 the environmental issues in business and marketing have driven out an issue of sensitivity towards the environment. Business not only in trading activities but advertisements which are related to Out of Home (OOH) Media is also taking up concern of out beating the traditional media of advertisements. Business strategies towards the media and promotional campaigns should also play a heed towards how advertisements are released and displayed amongst the people and their surroundings.

Every marketing manager has to play a key role in fostering, replacing and saving the natural resources. This could be done by adopting such kind of sustainable innovative approaches which would definitely benefit the organizations and the scenes of nature, the role of media related to outdoor means are also changing the methodology of displaying their ads. The campaigns done through Solar energy or any forms of renewable sources will surely act as a boon to the advertising agencies.

Although these concepts are found new, it is around the centuries human and marketers are driving themselves in reaching out new phenomenon in Out of Home (OOH) Media mediums.

Objective Of Study:

1. To Define and learn Out of Home (OOH)Media

2. To Study Sustainable approaches used by Out of Home Media

Research Methodology:

It is a descriptive study in which secondary data is collected from various forms like journals, magazines, blogs, references which helped to understand the concept of sustainable approaches used in Out of Home (OOH) Media advertising. The researcher conducted review of literature to identify the factors which could be adapted in Out of Home (OOH)Media

Definition:

- (Digital ideas) “Out-of-Home advertising is a traditional form of offline outdoor advertising that advertises to the audience at public spaces, commute stations & channels, commercial spaces, or even in places with the constant audience presence.”
- “Out of home advertising is interactive and attractive advertising empowered by digital channels & elements that are displayed in environments accessible to the public.”

Review Of Literature:

(Movia. media/sustainable-out-of-home-advertising) Taking the CO2 effect on the environment the Movia media has adopted to choose net zero emissions when the transits are on the move. They deal with ads on trucks that re channelized on their go to different Geopath. As the vehicles are moving the Out of Home (OOH) Media acts as an supportive tool for reaching the advertisements on the go.

(Latina journal of social communication 25.1.2000) The article explains advertisements which are usually used on billboards reflecting the Out of Home (OOH) Media, certain ethics need to be followed on maintaining the spirit of law on ads related to pharmaceuticals, tobacco, alcohol etc. There has to be special thoughts to be put up taking the teenagers and children so that it wouldn't cause any ill effects on fundamental rights such as health, privacy and image of planet and people.

(September 27, 2017 | [Sustainability](#) creating healthier building through mesh) The study reveals designers addressing safety of interiors and exteriors of the tall buildings which could be used as noticeable outdoor media which could

create an impact on the people on their go to. The business arena displays sound management, sunlight, biophilic architecture taking all sustainability into consideration

(15.3.2021 Fuente: Noticia Medio Ambiente) Research study explains an image displayed below with a dimension of 1000 square meter tries to generate purity in air from its nonpolluting effects. The Out of Home (OOH) Media advertisements is following all the norms of sustainability factors into consideration using a material titanium oxide a photocatalyst very nearby to photosynthesis generated by plants. It is a supportive model for ecosystem to downsize effects on global warming.

(JC Decaux Environment and OOH general trends) Research study says digital Out of Home (OOH) Media is being used to attract the goers taking sustainable norms by adopting low power requirements and using LED lights for showcasing ads. New innovation reflects all environment concerns and maintaining standard quality of green practices which will be designed for future uses.

Research Findings:

The information and the findings which the researcher collected has given a brief understanding of the importance of Sustainability and Out of Home (OOH) Media modes. It is the need of the hour that communication strategies used in advertisements should show cast eco-friendliest methods taking renewable energy which would not cause any harm on natural organism and there has to be survival for fittest.

Conclusions:

Review of past literature on Sustainability in Out of Home (OOH) Media Advertising has helped me in the generation of idea & knowledge of how new strategies are adopted by the firms to adjust according to the changing scenario. There are many information and studies available on methods related topic. The researcher got true insights into the study through various findings. The opinions shared by the experts, comments, helped to understand the gaps and design in research methodology for the study. There are various modes to identify the factors which might influence the factors of sustainability applied in OOH Media. The researcher also analysed the reasons behind foresee industries gearing up with fresh innovative strategies. One has to keep a approach of understanding the people process and planet study.

References:

- (Movia. media/sustainable-out-of-home-advertising) Blog
(Latina journal of social communication 25.1.2000)
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